

THE ANALYSIS OF LEGAL SERVICES: UNDERSTANDING ITS STRUCTURE AND IMPORTANCE

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Abstract. Legal services are an important part of the justice system, providing individuals and corporations with the advice and representation they require to overcome complex legal issues. Legal services cover a wide range of activities, from advising clients on their rights and duties to representing them in court proceedings. This research paper explores the complexities of legal services, analyzing the various types of services available and the significance of guaranteeing access to justice for everyone in the example of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: legal service, disciple, law enforcement

Introduction. Legal services are critical to preserving social order, justice, and the preservation of human rights. Law companies, attorneys, paralegals, and legal experts help individuals, businesses, and organizations negotiate difficult legal challenges, assure legal compliance, and seek justice.

Legal services encompass a broad spectrum of activities and assistance provided by legal professionals to individuals, businesses, and entities seeking legal advice, representation, and advocacy. These services may include legal consultations, contract drafting, litigation, dispute resolution, regulatory compliance, intellectual property protection, estate planning, and more. Legal services are essential for protecting rights, resolving conflicts, enforcing legal obligations, and upholding the rule of law in society.

Currently, legal service is becoming one of the practical means of strengthening the law and rule of law, discipline, and order and increasing the effectiveness of state bodies as a part of the mechanism of legal regulation of social relations. Therefore, the demand for legal entities and individuals is increasing. Before we study the legal

service and its activities in our country, let's first dwell on the meaning of “legal service” in detail. The concept of legal service consists of special actions and activities aimed at solving specific problems and has been interpreted differently by many legal scholars. In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 2017, No. PQ-2733 “On measures to radically improve the activity of the legal service” states, “Legal service is an independent structural structure or position that is established or introduced in a mandatory manner by the norms and criteria established by law to ensure the activities of state bodies and organizations legally”. In this case, legal services are a certain set of legal services provided by lawyers and aimed at protecting the interests and rights of clients.

Literature review. For many years, the role of the legal service in the establishment of a democratic legal state and the formation of civil society in our republic has been defined by the legal scientist Otakhanov Foziljon Haydarovich as follows: “Legal service is an organizationally independent structural unit that ensures the implementation of legal work in state power and management, economic management bodies, other economic entities (enterprises, institutions, and organizations) department, legal department, legal department, legal group, legal bureau) or specialist (chief legal consultant, leading legal consultant, senior legal consultant or legal consultant)”. As can be seen from the above definition, the legal service is a separate, independent structure that ensures the implementation of legal affairs in every state body, every legal entity, and every individual. Without legal services, it is difficult to provide the rule of law and justice in developing the new Uzbekistan.

Fayziyev Khayriddin Sirojiddinovich in his dissertation research on the topic “Improving the organizational and legal foundations of the legal service system in state administration bodies” is defined as follows: “legal services of state administration bodies, by ensuring legality in the practice of law enforcement, protecting the rights and legal interests of employees, improving their legal culture and literacy, property

and other interests of the state body through legal means the structural structure of the executive power aimed at ensuring its protection”.

Discussion. Legal services can be broadly categorized into several distinct areas, each serving a unique purpose in addressing the legal needs of clients. The following table provides an overview of common types of legal services:

- Legal Advice - Providing guidance and counsel on legal matters, including rights, obligations, and potential courses of action.

- Litigation Representation - Advocating for clients in court proceedings, including trials, hearings, and appeals.

- Transactional Services - Assisting with the drafting and review of legal documents, such as contracts, licenses, and deeds.

- Alternative Dispute Resolution - Facilitating negotiations and settlements outside of the courtroom, often through methods like mediation and arbitration.

According to Professor F.H. Otakhanov, the above definitions of legal service do not fully reveal its legal essence. That is why F.X. Otakhanov singles out the following three aspects of the legal service category:

- firstly, legal service is available not only in an organization or enterprise, but also in state power and management, economic management bodies, institutions.

- secondly, the legal service does not always function as a department, department, or other structural structure, and a staff legal consultant may also perform its functions.

- thirdly, the inclusion of only two tasks of the legal service in its concept leads to the neglect of its other tasks.

The Regulation “On the legal service of state bodies and organizations” was adopted based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 2017, No. PQ-2733 provides the structure of the legal service, which consists of as follow:

- legal department
- legal management

- legal section
- legal office
- or Chief Legal Counsel, Lead Legal Counsel, Senior Legal Counsel, or Legal Counsel from one state

Conclusion. In conclusion, legal services are integral to upholding the rule of law, protecting rights, and ensuring justice in society. The structure of legal services, comprising law firms, legal practitioners, and support staff, plays a critical role in delivering comprehensive legal assistance to clients. Access to quality legal services is paramount for individuals and businesses to navigate legal complexities, safeguard their rights, and seek redress in legal matters. By understanding the concept of legal services and their importance, individuals can make informed decisions, protect their legal interests, and uphold the principles of justice and fairness in society.

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